

CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES OF THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY IN GEORGIA

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ABSTRACT

The subject of our research is, on the one hand, the challenges of the circular economy and, on the other hand, the possibilities for its development and improvement in Georgia.

In this paper, we examine the circular economy as an economic model that radically changes the paradigm of resource use and consumption and creates opportunities for the efficient use of material and financial resources.

Since the population is actively involved in circular economic relations, it has a clearly defined social character and is oriented toward enhancing public welfare and improving living conditions.

Our research has shown that today, due to the high economic activity of businesses, the large volume of industrial and household waste in industrialized countries pollutes the soil and atmosphere, creating the basis for epidemics and ecological disasters.

In Georgia as well, the role and function of the circular economy are increasing. The imperatives in the economy are changing, requiring the transformation of stereotypes formed within our economic system, which should be followed by serious adjustments to the existing economic paradigm of Georgia.

During the research process, the emphasis was placed on the current state of the circular economy in Georgia and the problems that hinder its development.

The aim of the study is to demonstrate the necessity of implementing the circular economy in Georgia and the prospects for its future development.

Keywords: circular economy, implementation, waste management, social responsibility, ecological environment.

The circular economy is an economic model in which not only the secondary use of goods already consumed is carried out, but an innovative waste-management system is introduced. It implies the reuse, restoration, and recycling of waste, materials, and products through the use of modern, advanced technologies.

The circular economy provides a unique opportunity to increase production volumes without increasing the expenditures associated with it. Since the population is actively involved in the process of waste collection alongside businesses, such an economic model has a clearly expressed social vector and is oriented toward raising public welfare and improving living conditions.

The circular economy should be viewed as an economic model that radically changes the paradigm of resource use and consumption and aims at the efficient use of material and financial resources and opportunities.

By its immanent nature, the circular economy is purposeful, as it establishes the principles of economy and saving in the distribution of resources and enhances positive waste-management practices within the civil sector.

Traditional economies have been based for centuries on the excessive use of natural resources and energy — according to the principle “take and use,” which causes enormous harm to natural and energy resources and to countries’ ecological systems.

The efficiency of the circular economy lies in maximally reducing the volume of waste, increasing the lifespan of produced goods, and conserving nature.

Ecological problems in many countries around the world have revealed the dangers — especially in land

use — that arise from the irrational consumption of land.

The prominent French public figure and philosopher Jean-Jacques Rousseau, in his historical treatise *The Social Contract, or Principles of Political Right* (1762), notes that “humanity would have avoided many wars, crimes, and murders if the first person who fenced off a piece of land and said ‘this is mine’ had been told ‘no,’ because in his view, the wealth derived from the land belongs to everyone, while the land itself belongs to no one.”¹⁸

We believe that this idea expressed by Rousseau in the 18th century should often be reminded to the governments and landowners of those countries that relentlessly exploit land resources and cause tremendous harm to nature and the environment.

In the era of global warming and climate crises, the circular economy changes economic approaches. The principle of “reducing waste and increasing its reuse” becomes established. Such an economic model preserves the environment, reduces the demand for new raw materials and resources, and contributes to the creation of new jobs. The circular economy represents a civilizational choice for countries, based on the principle: “live frugally and create more wealth.”

Today, due to the high economic activity of businesses, the large volume of industrial and household waste in industrial countries pollutes the soil and atmosphere, which becomes the basis for epidemics and ecological disasters.

The role and function of the circular economy are increasing in saving and managing energy resources, since new concepts of urban development are formed

¹⁸ David Vekua, Alexandre Taliashvili – On the Need for Legal Regulation of the Economy in Georgia – Journal “New Economist,” 2024, p. 26.

during the design and construction of buildings, enterprises, and cities.

According to 2024 indicators, *‘‘the circulation rate in Georgia’s economy amounted to 1.3%, which means that Georgia’s economy is predominantly linear in nature and requires substantial modernization in this direction, as the majority of consumed resources are of primary origin.’’¹⁹

Georgia’s integration into the global economy requires a more active implementation of circular economy principles and stronger governmental encouragement of circular economy models within the business sector.

One of the key tasks for the successful implementation of the circular economy is the introduction of positive waste-management practices in the country. In this regard, Sweden stands out, *‘‘where only 1% of waste ends up in landfills annually, while the rest is either recovered or recycled. Waste-recycling rates are also high in Austria (63%), Germany (62%), Taiwan (60%), Singapore (59%), the United Kingdom (50%), and others.’’²⁰

Waste recycling, secondary use of resources, extending product lifespans, and introducing zero-waste technologies are not merely fashionable trends — for Georgia, these should become important factors for economic growth. To address this challenge, Georgia adopted the **Waste Management Code** in 2018, which opened the possibility for the circular economy to move to a new stage of development. The will of the Georgian government is undoubtedly important, but even more important is public support for the implementation of this will.

At this stage, Georgia’s municipal waste collection, recycling, and disposal systems require substantial reforms and alignment with international requirements and standards. *‘‘Using the calculated waste-generation index, the amount of municipal waste generated in cities and rural settlements in 2020 averaged 0.95 kg per capita per day in urban areas (excluding tourists) and 0.54 kg per capita per day in rural areas. The total amount of municipal waste generated in 2020 was 1,061,007 tons, of which 760,942 tons originated in cities and 300,065 tons in rural areas. In 2021, total municipal waste generation amounted to 1,104,952 tons — 768,257 tons in cities and 336,695 tons in rural areas.’’²¹

Waste-composition analysis conducted during the same period to determine the typical structure of generated waste streams shows that:

*‘‘municipal waste consists of organic waste (54.7%), plastic (13.8%), paper and cardboard (10.6%), textiles (4.1%), construction and demolition waste (2.5%), glass (2.3%), metals (1.4%), and other waste (11%).’’²²

As these indicators show, Georgia’s waste stream contains a large share of organic and recyclable materials, which creates favorable conditions for their circular use and recovery.

Introducing modern methods for the recycling and utilization of plastic waste is one of the major global challenges from an environmental standpoint. *‘‘Each year, approximately 300 million tons of plastic waste accumulate worldwide. Notably, only 9% of this waste has been recycled, 12% is incinerated, while the remaining 79% ends up in landfills. Considering that plastic production and consumption are expected to increase even further, it can be assumed that the environmental situation will continue to worsen.’’²³

Plastic waste management is also one of the major problems for Georgia. *‘‘The population of Georgia generates an average of approximately 29,000 tons of plastic waste annually, which accounts for 14.9% of total waste.’’²⁴

Waste management in Georgia is linked to numerous challenges, as the waste-collection system is not developed to a sufficient degree, particularly in rural areas. Consequently, many people dispose of waste in improvised dumpsites, rivers, or gorges.

For the successful implementation of the circular economy in Georgia, it is essential to have a coordinated action strategy between the government and society — a strategy tailored to the country’s needs and capacities.

The economic growth and creation of new jobs resulting from circularity in Georgia must not harm the ecological environment, as environmental protection is a prerequisite for establishing this type of economic model.

Improving the recycling of municipal solid waste is also of critical importance, as unsystematic use of landfills still remains common practice in Georgia.

It is also crucial to increase energy efficiency in businesses in Tbilisi and other major cities, improve land and water resource management, and enhance material productivity.

Circular innovation is a necessary component for creating a strong and innovative national system, one that bases its production and service processes on the principles of the circular economy. Equally important for implementing a circular economy is the establishment of a circular culture — turning circular habits and practices into social norms. Achieving this is possible only through improved education and qualifications in this field, public-information campaigns, and activities aimed at increasing transparency and monitoring.

Introducing circular regulations in Georgia requires the formation of a corresponding legislative framework that will consider: expanding the assortment

¹⁹ 2. ‘‘Circularity Guide for Georgia,’’ 2024. Prepared with the support of the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) and Sweden.

²⁰ 3. Ramaz Abesadze, Kristine Kuratashvili; Waste Management Strategy in Georgia – Ecology, 06/28/2024.

²¹ National Waste Management Strategy of Georgia 2016–2030, p. 7

²² National Waste Management Strategy of Georgia 2016–2030, p. 7

²³ ISET Economists – G. Lobzhanidze, N. Piniati, ‘‘How Should Georgia Manage Plastic Waste?’’

<https://iset-pi.ge/ka/blog/66-rogor-unda-gaumklavdes-saqartvelo-plastmasis-narchenebs>

²⁴ ISET Economists – G. Lobzhanidze, N. Piniati, ‘‘How Should Georgia Manage Plastic Waste?’’

<https://iset-pi.ge/ka/blog/66-rogor-unda-gaumklavdes-saqartvelo-plastmasis-narchenebs>

of goods produced by businesses; promoting the reuse and recovery of waste; encouraging waste separation at the source; ensuring management infrastructure; developing regenerative agricultural production; and expanding secondary markets for local materials.

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